

Improving the viability of probiotics by encapsulation methods for development of functional dairy products

Safeer Ahmad^{*1}, Hafiz Nabeel Ahmad¹, Ghayyoor Ahmad², M. Saad Akram¹

¹National Institute of Food Science and Technology, Faculty of Food, Nutrition and Home Sciences, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan

²Institute of Animal and Dairy Sciences, Faculty of Animal Husbandry, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan

Key words: Probiotic dairy products, Functional foods, Probiotics, Encapsulation

Article Published: 23 October 2020

Abstract

The popularity of functional foods among scientists and common people has been increasing day by day. Awareness and modernization make the consumer think better regarding food and nutrition. Now a day's individual knows very well about the relation between food consumption and disease prevalence. Humans have a diversity of microbes in the gut that together form the gut microflora. Probiotics are the health-promoting live microbial cells improve host health through gut and brain connection and fighting against harmful bacteria. *Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacillus* are the two bacterial genera which are considered to be probiotic. These good bacteria are facing challenges of viability. There are so many factors such as sensitivity to heat, pH, acidity, osmotic effect, mechanical shear, chemical components, freezing and storage time as well which affects the viability of probiotics in the dairy food matrix as well as in the gut. Multiple efforts have been done in the past and ongoing in present for these beneficial microbial population stability until their destination in the gut. One of a useful technique known as microencapsulation makes the probiotic effective in the diversified conditions and maintain these microbe's community to the optimum level for achieving targeted benefits. Dairy products are found to be an ideal vehicle for probiotic incorporation. It has been seen that the encapsulated microbial cells show higher viability than the free cells in different processing and storage conditions as well as against bile salts in the gut. They make the food functional when incorporated, without affecting the product sensory characteristics.

*Corresponding Author: Safeer Ahmad ✉ safeerahmad902@gmail.com

Introduction

Food provides energy for growth and development. Presently, consumers have serious concern due to their understanding regarding diet consumption and health in diet selection. The demand for functional foods has been increased (Tripathi and Giri, 2014). Food is said to be a functional food, which exerts additional positive health effects along with nourishing the host (Siro *et al.*, 2008; Prosapio *et al.*, 2016). Different functional ingredients such as probiotics and prebiotics are used in functional foods. Functional foods are lactose-free and provide a lot of health benefits (Chuayana *et al.*, 2003; Suvarna and Boby, 2005).

Functional foods exert positive effects on mood and behaviour, regulate the physical activity, antioxidant and improve immune functions (Lin, 2003). However, probiotic functional food products facing issues for the survival of the probiotic at different stages of production (Boylston *et al.*, 2004). Different functional foods such as probiotics dairy products are available. In fact, the phrase “You are what you eat” compel the people for consumption of functional foods (Verbeke, 2005). Fermented milk products are being used for their nutritional as well as the therapeutic role (Roberfroid, 1999). To incorporate dairy products with probiotics (good bacteria) is such a big task for the researcher as well as for industry (Karthikyan *et al.*, 2014).

Probiotics are the living microorganism which provides numerous health benefits to the consumers when ingested to an adequate extent. *Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacillus* are the two bacterial genera (Solanki *et al.*, 2013) which are commonly used in the preparation of ready to eat (RTE) functional foods (Gawkowski and Chikindas, 2013). Both genera are GRAS (Siro *et al.*, 2008). Probiotics boost up the immunity when ingested to an adequate amount and protect against various diseases (Collado *et al.*, 2009). Probiotics prevent the intestine from pathogenic bacteria and prevention against intestinal infection (Tuomola *et al.*, 2006). In fact, Probiotic strains are specific in their function and exert positive health effects to the host (Oelschlaeger, 2010). The probiotic food products must be safe and

have a significant viable number at the time of utilization. According to recommendations, viable probiotics bacteria should be present in the product at a minimum level from 10^6 to 10^7 CFU/ml or g for their best performance. Functional foods have the economic scope and huge market gains. Market share of probiotic functional foods contribute about 60% to 70% (Holzapfel, 2006; Kołozyn-Krajewskaa and Dolatowski, 2012; Stanton *et al.*, 2001). Several probiotic dairy products have been developed such as dairy beverages, dairy desserts, flavored milk, powder milk, buttermilk, fermented milk, sour cream, baby foods, ice cream, cheese and yoghurt. (Mohammadi and Mortazavian, 2011). Fermented milk-based products are good tools for the incorporation of probiotics but viability losses occur at different stages of production, freezing and storage. Viability losses are more in freezing than storage process. (Mohammadi *et al.*, 2011). The use of functional ingredients (probiotics) in the products have been increasing day by day (Karthikeyan *et al.*, 2013).

There are so many factors such as sensitivity to heat, pH, acidity, osmotic effect, mechanical shear, chemical components, freezing and storage time (Krasaekoopt *et al.*, 2003; Martin *et al.*, 2015) which affects the viability of probiotics in the dairy products. These factors motivate researchers to develop some innovative methods for their survival in the product as well in G.I system (Luckow and Delahunty, 2004). Encapsulation may enhance the survivability of probiotics in the product and the G.I tract as well (Mohammadi *et al.*, 2011). Microencapsulation (ME) is a technique to augment the viability of probiotics (Heidebach *et al.*, 2012) and considered very effective (Martin *et al.*, 2015). Microencapsulation is wrapping the probiotics to save them from external environment (Sultana *et al.*, 2000). The most appropriate and usually used wrapping material is Alginate (Krasaekoopt *et al.*, 2004). Encapsulation reduces injury to bacteria and protects probiotics against bacteriophages (Burgain *et al.*, 2011). The aim of this current review is to highlight the probiotic overview, factors affecting their survivability in various conditions, materials and methods used for encapsulation and some probiotic foods, especially fermented dairy products.

Probiotics

Probiotics are well known for their various health possession activities (Kerry *et al.*, 2018). Beneficial microbes have been used in the fermentation of different products for a long time ago (Cross *et al.*, 2001). By the definition of probiotic, promote the health of the host when dispensing to a sufficient extent (Bagchi, 2014). At industrial scale, probiotics illustrated as “live microbes being the part of product exhibiting health advantages” (Clancy, 2003). Prerequisites, for the microorganisms to be appraised as “probiotics” it should retain viability in the product as well as in the stomach and gastrointestinal tract (G.I), present in sufficient number for its activity at the delivery site (Hyun and Shin, 1998),

Benefits of probiotics

Probiotics have an application to be eaten as a pharmaceutical product or be administered in nutraceuticals and functional foods (Hoch and Saad, 2009; Radulović *et al.*, 2017). These beneficial microorganisms improve immune functions (Song *et al.*, 2013), prevent the intestine from pathogenic bacteria (Jandhyala *et al.*, 2015; Tsai *et al.*, 2019) as well as prevent against intestinal infection (Tuomola *et al.*, 2006). Probiotics exceed food nutritional value by increasing their bioavailability and enhance lactose digestion (Marco *et al.*, 2010), reduce blood pressure as well as lower serum lipids proportion. By the gut-brain connection they have importance in the disorder of mood, mitigate anxiety (Huang *et al.*, 2016; Messaoudi *et al.*, 2011) and depression (Huang *et al.*, 2016).

Probiotics also have a therapeutic role such as reduce the chances of cancer by binding the carcinogens (Rasic, 2003). They also ameliorate lactose intolerance, treat diarrhoea (Reid, 2015; Appel-da-Silva *et al.*, 2017) and prevent urinogenital diseases (Lourens-Hattingh and Viljoen, 2001; Mattila-Sandholm *et al.*, 2002). Probiotics (a mixture of *L. rhamnosus*, *B. breve* and *P. freudenreichii*) used to minimize inflammatory bowel diseases (Bakirtzi *et al.*, 2016). They were found to be better in comparison of placebo in treating the irritable bowel syndrome (Kajander *et al.*, 2005). Probiotics (*B. breve*, *L. casei* and *L. plantarum*) have been used to

treat the patient from infection after surgery and significantly reduce postoperative bacterial infections (Rayaes *et al.*, 2005; Kanazawa *et al.*, 2005).

Probiotics have their important role to treat and prevent some allergic diseases (Begum *et al.*, 2017) such as specific strains of *L. rhamnosus*, *B. longum* and *L. Reuteri* remarkably diminish the rhinorrhea and eczema after treating the host with such probiotics strains to about 6 months (Kalliomaki *et al.*, 2001; Rosenfeldt *et al.*, 2004).

Well known probiotics

There are several species and genera of microorganisms evaluated as prospective “probiotics” (Shah and Ravula, 2004). Several species of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) and non-lactic acid and some yeasts remain viable in the intestine and exhibit adequate health activities (Holzefel *et al.*, 2006). Chiefly used bacterial genera are *Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacillus* (both are gram-positive and anaerobic). Both genera are designated as GRAS (generally recognized as safe) and have their habitat in the intestine of humans (Boumis *et al.*, 2018).

Others bacteria used as probiotics are belonging to the genera *Streptococcus*, *Lactococcus*, *Propionibacterium*, *Bacillus*, *Enterococcus* and *Pediococcus*. Some yeasts such as *Saccharomyces boulardii*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and fungi (*Aspergillus oryzae*) deliberating health-promoting effects to host are evaluated as probiotics. (Rivera-Espinoza and Gallardo-Navarro, 2010; Vinderola and Reinheimer, 2003; Fijan, 2014; Tsai *et al.*, 2019).

Probiotics selection

In fact, *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* are commercially used bacterial genera. Probiotics strains selection is such a worthwhile consideration to uproot some major health-related benefits. Several determinants should be considered to choose bacterial strains as probiotics. Adequate amount and appropriate strains selection for the development of probiotics food products is some prerequisites, which should remain viable during processing and storage as well as in stomach and gastrointestinal tract (Ventura and Perozzi, 2011).

Specific bacterial strains have certain effects and have the ability to bear harsh processing operations, survive at low pH in the stomach and G.I tract as well as in food matrices. *Lactobacillus* (most probably occurs in fermented products) strains have more resistibility against such conditions than *Bifidobacteria*. Due to such ability they have more uses regarding technological aspects in the food industry (Tripathi and Giri, 2014).

Probiotic Doses

Different probiotic strains are commercially available in the market in the form of a variety of fermented products (*S. thermophilus* as culture in fermented milk and yoghurt) and in capsule (*L. rhamnosus*, *B. longum*, *B. bifidum*) as well (Fuller, 1992). Probiotics confer health benefits only in case when present in ample quantity and retain their viability. So, it's necessary to declare their suitable count at different stages for their effectiveness. Probiotics minimum viable count in the product should be as low as 10⁶ CFU/g or mL (Boylston *et al.*, 2004), probiotics must be consumed daily at the rate of 10⁸ CFU/day (Lopez-Robio *et al.*, 2006) and their minimum count should be 10⁷ CFU/mL at the point of action (Doleyres and Lacroix, 2005; Tripathi and Giri, 2014).

Factors affecting probiotics viability and survival

Bacteria to be a probiotic, it's a necessary to remain viable and survive in the product in active form to its enough population at the time of utilization for its beneficiary effects to host health (Korbekandi *et al.*, 2011). So, their viability was found to be a supreme Importance for action. Several parameters were found, which significantly affects the probiotic viability and survival rate in the food products during different stages of production until consumption.

Some known factors like food factors (amount of sugar and salt, pH, dissolved oxygen, water activity, H₂O₂, a fermentation by-product, acidity), processing factors such as exposure to heat, cooling, incubation time and temperature, use of anti-microbial ingredients, freezing, drying, material used in packaging and storage environment and microbial factors (probiotics strains and amount used) creates challenges to

probiotic survival (Tripathi and Giri, 2014). Food matrix is important for probiotic incorporation.

Selection of appropriate food product is a vehicle to carry probiotic, much necessary for their viability. Low stomach pH and bile acid secretions into the G.I tract such an inappropriate environment for probiotic to be functional and maintain viability. They would have to show metabolic activity and resist susceptibility to enzymatic degradation (Ranadheera *et al.*, 2012).

To overcome the probiotic viability issues in different harsh conditions of food manufacturing and in G.I tract, there is a serious need of technological advancement to develop such techniques, which enhance probiotic survival and viability in such competitive environment to perform functions (Mattila-Sandholm *et al.*, 2011). Microencapsulation is an advanced method to augment the probiotic viability (Philips *et al.*, 2006). Its makes probiotic to be viable even in an acidic environment and functional in the food matrix as well.

Microencapsulation

It's an important technique in which the defined substance is just entrapped into a specific material to form a capsule ranges from few millimetres to nanometres, a protective covering membrane save the transferring material from outer severe environmental conditions (Vivek, 2013). Microencapsulation is such an effective approach to make sure the safe transfer of probiotic microorganisms to the target site. It ensures their viability during processing and storages as well as in the G.I tract (Cook *et al.*, 2013). The main purpose is to separate the reactive substances from unfavourable surroundings.

The technology of encapsulation enhance the survival of live microbes against unfavourable conditions such as high bile salt concentrations, oxygen, achieve longer shelf life, reduces evaporation rate (Borgogna *et al.*, 2010; Madene *et al.*, 2006). It protects the material as well as permits the controlled release in the intestine in biologically active form (Zuidam and Shimoni, 2009) and immobilization of cell results in uniform apportionment all over the product (Krasaekoopt *et al.*, 2003).

There are several challenges in the development of probiotic microcapsule, one of them is their size (diameter about 1-5 μ m) exert difficulties in advancement, which directly inhibit nanotechnologies. Larger capsule size negatively influence the properties of food products. Even different methods of encapsulation applied gives heterogeneous capsule size ranges and shapes (De Vos *et al.*, 2010). Physicochemical characteristics of encapsulated material greatly affect probiotic viability and concentration as well. The most pivotal is the selection of probiotic strains (Krishnan *et al.*, 2005).

This unique technology is accomplished into three steps. The first step is to assimilate the bioactive material in matrix which may be liquid or solid. If the encapsulated material is liquid, incorporation will be dissolution but if the material is solid it would be adsorption. Next and second step involves liquid matrix dispersion. Third and the last step involves stabilization by a gelification, physical (solidification, coalescence) and chemical (polymerization) method (Poncelet and draffier, 2007). After encapsulation of microbial cells the micro-beads are formed having a resemblance to that of oval and spherical shapes. Every single bead retains one to diverse numbers of bacterial cells (Zinedine and Faid, 2007).

Studies revealed the effect of encapsulation of microbial cell in comparison to free cell. Encapsulated strains of *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* exhibit better stability to low stomach pH (2.0) and bile salts and reached to about 58.9% mean value in contrast to non-encapsulated cells (Champagne *et al.*, 2015). Acidic pH, lactic acid concentration, high amount of molecular oxygen and hydrogen peroxide makes the environment unfit for probiotic persistence in the dairy products. Microencapsulation enables them to linger in such an unfriendly surrounding (Picot and Lacroix, 2004).

Free cells of bacterial strains of *L. acidophilus* LA-5 and *Bifidobacterium lactis* BB-12 should not survive in the fermented dairy drinks at pH<4.2 after fortnight period of storage and their viable count were restricted to 10² CFU ml⁻¹. But when both strains were encapsulated

their viable populace increased and remain viable in such habitat (Mortazavian *et al.*, 2008).

Encapsulated material

Material being used in encapsulation should be safe, non-toxic and food grade (Ei-Salam and Ei-shibiny, 2012). Polymers (starch, chitosan, gelatine), celluloses (CMC), gums (xanthan gum, Gum arabic), milk proteins (casein and whey) and fats are extensively used materials in microencapsulation (Mokarram *et al.*, 2009; Chavarri *et al.*, 2010; Cook *et al.*, 2013).

Starch

Starch is a polysaccharide made up of the large number of glucose units connected through glucosidic linkage. Amylose and amylopectin comprise starch composition. Resistant starch is a type of starch which is indigestible by pancreatic enzymes (Sajilata *et al.*, 2006). Moreover, resistant starch permit the control liberation to the intestine causes good microbial survival in this type of application (Naulkaekul and Charalampopoulos, 2011). Due to such successful survival of bacteria, it is appreciably used in the food industry (Anal and Singh, 2007).

Chitosan

In the presence of anions and poly anions glucosamine molecules cross-link to form a linear polymer known as chitosan. Chitosan itself is not effective for encapsulation, but it is good coating material. It gives excellent protection in G.I tract when used in combination with alginate (Mortazavian *et al.*, 2008; Chavarri *et al.*, 2010).

Gelatin

It is a non-toxic, commercially available and valuable material used for microencapsulation. Usually obtained from bones having good protective properties (Imeson, 1997). It is observed to be a protein gum forming a thermoreversible gel. Due to its amphoteric nature it can be used in combination with other ionic polysaccharides like gellan gum (Sendra *et al.*, 2008).

Milk proteins

Milk proteins like whey protein have excellent gelling and emulsifying properties (Cayot and Lorient, 1997).

Moreover, physicochemical characteristics of milk protein enables them good carrier matrix for probiotics. Biologically it's a good material for probiotic encapsulation (Livney, 2010).

Gum Arabic

A plant source gum highly soluble in water and have low viscosity. It is a good encapsulation material which maintain the original characters of the core material and keep the probiotic survivability in storage (Reyes *et al.*, 2018). It does not affect the organoleptic properties of the product and resist to processing and acidic conditions (Kravtchenko, 1998).

Alginate

A naturally occurring polysaccharide consist of beta-D-mannuronic acid and alpha-L-glucuronic acid (Sohail *et al.*, 2011). For encapsulation of microbial cell alginate is extensively used (Hansen *et al.*, 2002). Calcium and Sodium alginate are most commonly used due to non-toxicity and economical price (Krasaekoopt *et al.*, 2003). Sodium alginate is most suitable material for probiotic encapsulation due to high retention of viability, heat stability, readily form gel and naturally occurring (Lee and Heo, 2000). Using Alginate is disadvantage is that beads produced are sensitive to acidic conditions, but this can be overcome by applying another coating or mixing with other material or applying additives (Krasaekoopt *et al.*, 2003).

Encapsulated methods

Extrusion method

A physical approach to protect probiotic to maintain its integrity. It's a simple and economical process causes no damage to microbial cell (Krasaekoopt *et al.*, 2003). Prepared hydrocolloid suspension (Na or Ca alginate in water) having probiotic strains in it. It is entitled to pass through a narrow opening under pressure. Droplets thus formed are collected in a hardening solution of CaCl₂ and permit to stay in solution about an half-hour. The solution is then centrifuged to separate the micro-beads for further application or stored at 39.2 °F. Some challenges to use this method. First, it form beads at very slow rate and the second one is that the bead produced are relatively larger in size which disturbs the product

textural attributes (Kailasapathy, 2009; De Vos *et al.*, 2010; Jayalalilha *et al.*, 2011).

Spray drying and spray freeze-drying method

The operational procedure for both of these methods is same except solidification of the micro beads. Suspension of probiotic cells and polymer is projected to form mist in controlled chamber by atomizing the mixture through nozzle. Rapidity of the method and acceptable for industrial implementation are pros of the method. In case of spray drying the solvent is vaporized by hot gas in the chamber and micro-capsule is obtained by cyclone separator. Whereas, in spray freeze drying frozen droplets are obtained in a freezing chamber and dried through freeze-drying. Cons of both of these methods are that additional coating is required for protection against surroundings (Semyonov *et al.*, 2010; Kailasapathy, 2009; Zuidam and Shimoni, 2009).

Emulsification Method

This chemical method of emulsification involves two phases, one is continuous (oil) and other is discontinuous (mixture of probiotic and coated material) phase are involved. Mixture of both phases is then homogenized to make water-in-oil emulsions or oil-in-water emulsions. Emulsifier and surfactant are added for emulsion stability. For solidification CaCl₂ is added. This method is easy to scale-up but beads produced are relatively larger size that is undesirable (Chen and Chen, 2007; Kailasapathy, 2009; De Vos *et al.*, 2010).

Probiotic foods

Numerous food products have been developed to be claimed as probiotics. Several qualitative parameters should be considered in the development of probiotic food products such as it should be safe, have unique sensory characteristics, economical, beneficial to health and have enough population of such beneficial microbial cells for effectiveness at target point (Rose *et al.*, 2005; Burgain *et al.*, 2011). During the recent decades trend has been increased in the development of probiotic (cheeses, buttermilk, yoghurt and ice cream) dairy products (Radulović *et al.*, 2017).

Following are some commercially available probiotic dairy based food products which are overviewed.

Yoghurt

Probiotic, the live microbes are poorly adopted to yoghurt because of vulnerability to low pH (4.2-4.6). Microencapsulation found to be much better approach for their persistence in such competitive environment (Kailasapathy, 2009). Greek style lactose free probiotic yoghurt were prepared which proved good survivability of encapsulated probiotic strains over one month storage at 4°C (Pinto *et al.*, 2019). Two strains of *Bifidobacterium* (*B.breve* 070, *B.longum* R023) when encapsulated using whey protein by spray drying technique, exhibits remarkable viability at low yoghurt pH (stored at 4°C for 4 weeks) and in-vitro digestion in contrast to free cells (Arnaud Picot and Christophe Lacroix, 2004). Effects of microencapsulation on strains of *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* *ssp.* shows high rate of viability than non-encapsulated strains. The reduction in serviceability of *B. infantis*17930 and *L. Rhamnosus* GG was 0.07 log, while that of *L. casei* 1520 number lowered by 0.28 log and *B.longum* 1941 was decreased by 0.39 log. Alginate based microencapsulation enhance viability of combined selected probiotic by 0.31 log in freeze-dried yoghurt after 28 days storage at 21°C (Capela *et al.*, 2006).

Yoghurt was prepared from goat milk using encapsulated strains besides free strains of *Bifidobacterium* along with prebiotic insulin. Results showed good survival of encapsulated combination of probiotic with prebiotic in goat milk yoghurt (Pradeep Prasanna and charalampopoulos, 2019). Moreover study investigated that symbiotic microcapsule of *S. thermophiles* and *L. bulgaricus* in yoghurt remained viable to standard count than free-state (Wattananapakasem *et al.*, 2018). However, studies shows that the problem exist in the larger size (22 to 50µm) of the capsule cause's grittiness in mouth which is undesirable in the product (Adhikari *et al.*, 2003). The issue can be mitigated by developing the technologies that may produce the minimum capsule size to improve the textural characteristics.

Cheese

Cheese is one of the nutritional and fermented dairy product suitable for the consumption of all age groups. It creates buffer in gut against acidic environment. Additionally such type of food matrix impart suitable protection for survivability in stomach (Ross *et al.*, 2002; Bergamini *et al.*, 2005). Cheese found to be good food matrix for probiotic incorporation because of its high value of pH (5.5) especially the cheddar cheese. Moreover its high fat content lowers the probiotic susceptibility to low pH and degradation by enzymes. Beads of microbial strains of *Bifidobacterium bifidum* were obtained by emulsion method. It was found that there was no significant change in sensory attributes of cheddar cheese after 24 weeks of storage in contrast to control. Even *Bifidobacterium* survive at low ripening temperature (6-7°C) and persist for 6 months (Dinakar and Mistry, 1994). Literature showed that supplementation of microencapsulated probiotic strains of *L. paracasei* maintained their viability in feta cheese to their optimum population (Kia *et al.*, 2018). The viability of *L. plantarum* 564 was checked in both free and encapsulated form by spray dried method in soft goat cheese over a period of 2 month. Results were in favor of encapsulated form that exhibited higher viability (Radulović *et al.*, 2017). Another study confirmed the encapsulated probiotic stability higher than free cell in the cream cheese (Ningtyas *et al.*, 2019). Work was done on encapsulation of *L. acidophilus* showed higher viability in Manaba cheese than free strains at 25 °C (Santacruz and Castro, 2018). Microencapsulated *L.acidophilic* (LA-5) remained viable in UF white cheese (Nejati *et al.*, 2017).

Ice cream

Ice cream is a popular dairy product and consumed worldwide and popular among people of all age especially in children's. To enhance its nutritional value is a serious concern of today research. Probiotic added to ice cream do not affect its sensory profile except slightly show acidic characters causing sour taste (Salem *et al.*, 2005). Study was conducted to evaluate the effect of microencapsulation on microbial viability. Experiments showed that

encapsulated probiotic showed high survival rate more than 30 percent as compared to free probiotic cell in ice cream without effecting its sensory characteristics (Karthikeyan *et al.*, 2014). Bacteria incorporated to ice cream face harsh challenges to variety of technological procedure. To combat such problems they were encapsulated for their survivability in variety of conditions and remain biologically active.

The viability of two bacterial strains *L. casei* (NCDC-298) and *Bifidobacterium animalis ssp. Lactis* (BB-12) was tested in four types of ice cream in encapsulated and non-encapsulated form. The viable count for *Lactobacillus casei* was $5.3 \pm 0.2 \times 10^9$ cfu/ml at first day and then reduced to $4.5 \pm 0.2 \times 10^6$ cfu/ml after 180 days of storage. $4.6 \pm 0.2 \times 10^9$ cfu/ml was viable count for *Bifidobacterium animalis ssp. Lactis* at first day and then lessen to $2.1 \pm 0.1 \times 10^7$ cfu/ml after 180 days of storage at -23°C . Encapsulation of these strains using calcium alginate enhance their viability up to 30 percent under similar conditions without affecting organoleptic properties of ice-cream (Karthikeyan *et al.*, 2013). It has been evaluated that the probiotic strains of *B. adolescentis* and *L. casei* improved viability to their standard count by microencapsulation in ice cream without effecting product sensorial attributes after storage up-to 100 days (Zanjani *et al.*, 2018). Study evaluated the probiotic viability and similar results were obtained by Champagne *et al.* (2015) and Afzaal *et al.* (2019).

Conclusion

Dairy food products are found to have an ideal profile of food matrix for safe delivery of probiotic living cells to the gut and proliferate their growth. High fat content of dairy products provide protection to living microbial cell in the G.I tract up to limit. Their viability issues have been resolved to a certain extent by using the advance technology of microencapsulation, which enables them to remain biologically active till consumption to accomplish their functions and provide control release and ultimately they promote the host health. But bacterial size causes obstruction in probiotic food product development which ultimately diminish sensory

attributes of the product. So, its dire need to develop more innovative technologies for production of Nano-size capsule, for incorporation to the product.

Recommendations

The care should be taken in selection of material for coating and interaction among matrix, encapsulation material as well as probiotics should be evaluated for long term stability of probiotics and product safety. Besides, their viability should be assessed in G.I transit as *In-vivo* and *in-vitro* models for probiotic efficacy.

Abbreviation

GRAS (generally recognize as safe), G.I. (gastrointestinal)

References

- Adhikari K, Mustapha A, Grün IU.** 2003. Survival and metabolic activity of microencapsulated *Bifidobacterium* in stirred yogurt. Journal of Food Science **68(1)**, 275- 280.
- Afzaal M, Saeed F, Arshad MU, Nadeem MT, Saeed M, Tufail T.** 2019. The effect of encapsulation on the stability of probiotic bacteria in ice cream and simulated gastrointestinal conditions. Probiotics and Antimicrobial Proteins **11(4)**, 1348-1354.
- Anal AK, Singh H.** 2007. Recent advances in microencapsulation of probiotics for industrial applications and targeted delivery. Trends in Food Science and Technology **18(5)**, 240-251.
- Appel-da-Silva MC, Narvaez GA, Perez LR, Drehmer L, Lewgoy J.** 2017. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* var. *boulardii* fungemia following probiotic treatment. Medical Mycology Case Reports **18**, 15-17.
- Bagchi T.** 2014. Traditional food and modern lifestyle: Impact of probiotics. The Indian journal of Medical Research **140(3)**, 333.
- Bakirtzi K, Law IKM, Xue X, Iliopoulos D, Shah YM, Pothoulakis C.** 2016. Neurotensin promotes the development of colitis and intestinal angiogenesis via Hif-1 α -miR-210 signaling. The Journal of Immunology **196 (10)**, 4311- 4321.

- Begum PS, Madhav G, Rajagopal S, Viswanath B, Razak MA, Venkataratnamma V.** 2017. Probiotics as functional foods: potential effects on human health and its impact on neurological diseases. *International Journal of Nutrition, Pharmacology, Neurological Diseases* **7 (2)**, 23.
- Bergamini CV, Hynes ER, Quiberoni A, Suarez VB, Zalazar CA.** 2005. Probiotic bacteria as adjunct starters: influence of the addition methodology on their survival in a semi-hard Argentinean cheese. *Food Research International* **38**, 597- 604.
- Borgogna M, Bellich B, Zorzin L, Lapasin R, Cesàro A.** 2010. Food microencapsulation of bioactive compounds: Rheological and thermal characterisation of non-conventional gelling system. *Food Chemistry* **122(2)**, 416- 423.
- Boumis E, Capone A, Galati V, Venditti C, Petrosillo N.** 2018. Probiotics and infective endocarditis in patients with hereditary hemorrhagic telangiectasia: a clinical case and a review of the literature. *BMC Infectious Diseases* **18(1)**, 65.
- Boylston TD, Vinderola CG, Ghoddusi HB, Reinheimer JA.** 2004. Incorporation of *bifidobacteria* into cheeses: challenges and rewards. *International Dairy Journal* **14(5)**, 375- 387.
- Burgain J, Gaiani C, Linder M, Scher J.** 2011. Encapsulation of probiotic living cells: From laboratory scale to industrial applications. *Journal of Food Engineering*. **104 (4)**, 467- 483.
- Capela P, Hay TKC, Shah NP.** 2006. Effect of cryoprotectants, prebiotics and microencapsulation on survival of probiotic organisms in yoghurt and freeze-dried yoghurt. *Food Research International* **39(2)**, 203-211.
- Cayot P, Lorient DE.** 1997. Structure-function relationships of whey proteins. *Food Science and Technology*-New York-Marcel Dekker 225- 256.
- Champagne CP, Raymond Y, Guertin N, Bélanger G.** 2015. Effects of storage conditions, microencapsulation and inclusion in chocolate particles on the stability of probiotic bacteria in ice cream. *International Dairy Journal* **47**, 109-117.
- Chavarri M, Maranon I, Ares R, Ibanez FC, Marzo F, Villaran MDC.** 2010. Microencapsulation of a probiotic and prebiotic in alginate-chitosan capsules improves survival in simulated gastro-intestinal conditions. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* **142(1-2)**, 185-189.
- Chen MJ, Chen KN.** 2007. Applications of probiotic encapsulation in dairy products. *Encapsulation and Controlled Release Technologies in Food Systems* 83-107.
- Chuayana EL, Ponce CV, Rivera RB, Cabrera EC.** 2003. Antimicrobial activity of probiotics from milk products. *Journal of Microbiology and Infectious Diseases* **32(2)**, 71-74.
- Clancy R.** 2003. Immunobiotics and the probiotic evolution. *FEMS Immunology and Medical Microbiology* **38 (1)**, 9-12.
- Collado MC, Isolauri E, Salminen S, Sanz Y.** 2009. The impact of probiotic on gut health. *Current Drug Metabolism* **10(1)**, 68-78.
- Cook MT, Tzortzis G, Khutoryanskiy VV, Charalampopoulos D.** 2013. Layer-by-layer coating of alginate matrices with chitosan-alginate for the improved survival and targeted delivery of probiotic bacteria after oral administration. *Journal of Materials Chemistry B* **1(1)**, 52- 60.
- Cross ML, Stevenson LM, Gill HS.** 2001. Anti-allergy properties of fermented foods: an important immune regulatory mechanism of lactic acid bacteria? *International Immunopharmacology* **1(5)**, 891- 901.
- De Vos P, Faas MM, Spasojevic M, Sikkema J.** 2010. Encapsulation for preservation of functionality and targeted delivery of bioactive food components. *International Dairy Journal* **20(4)**, 292-302.

- Dinakar P, Mistry VV.** 1994. Growth and viability of *Bifidobacterium bifidum* in cheddar cheese. *Journal of Dairy Science* **77(10)**, 2854-2864.
- Doleyres Y, Lacroix C.** 2005. Technologies with free and immobilised cells for probiotic *bifidobacteria* production and protection. *International Dairy Journal* **15(10)**, 973- 988.
- Fijan S.** 2014. Microorganisms with claimed probiotic properties: an overview of recent literature. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* **11(5)**, 4745- 4767.
- Fuller R.** 1992. Probiotics. The Scientific Basis. 1st Ed. Chapman and Hall Ltd. London, UK. 398.
- Gawkowski D, Chikindas ML.** 2013. Non-dairy probiotic beverages: the next step into human health. *Beneficial Microbes* **4(2)**, 127-142.
- Hansen LT, Allan-Wojtas PM, Jin YL, Paulson AT.** Survival of Ca-alginate microencapsulated *Bifidobacterium spp.* in milk and simulated gastrointestinal conditions. *Food Microbiology* **19(1)**, 35-45.
- Heidebach T, Forst P, Kulozik U.** 2012. Microencapsulation of probiotic cells for food applications. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition* **52(4)**, 291- 311.
- Hoch C, Saad S.** 2009. Viability of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* La-5 added solely or in co-culture with a yoghurt starter culture and implication on physico-chemical and related properties of Minas fresh cheese during storage. *Food Science and Technology* **42**, 633- 640.
- Holzappel WH, Goktepe I, Juneja VK, Ahmedna M.** 2006. Introduction to prebiotics and probiotics. *Probiotics in Food Safety and Human Health* **35(2)**, 109-116.
- Huang R, Wang K, Hu J.** 2016. Effect of probiotics on depression: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Nutrients* **8(8)**, 483.
- Hyun CK, Shin HK.** 1998. Utilization of bovine plasma obtained from a slaughterhouse for economic production of probiotics. *Journal of Fermentation and Bioengineering* **86(1)**, 34-37.
- Jandhyala SM, Talukdar R, Subramanyam C, Vuyyuru H, Sasikala M, Reddy DN.** 2015. Role of the normal gut microbiota. *World Journal of Gastroenterology* **21(29)**, 8787.
- Jayalalitha V, Dorai RP, Dhanalakshmi B, Elango A, Kumar CN.** 2011. Improving the viability of probiotics in yoghurt through different methods of encapsulation. *Egyptian Journal of Dairy Science* **39(1)**, 39- 44.
- Kailasapathy K.** 2009. Encapsulation technologies for functional foods and nutraceutical product development. *CAB Reviews: Perspectives in Agriculture, Veterinary Science, Nutrition and Natural Resources* **4 (33)**, 1- 19.
- Kajander K, Hatakka K, Poussa T, Färkkilä M, Korpela R.** 2005. A probiotic mixture alleviates symptoms in irritable bowel syndrome patients: a controlled 6-month intervention. *Alimentary Pharmacology and Therapeutics* **22(5)**, 387- 394.
- Kalliomäki M, Salminen S, Arvilommi H, Kero P, Koskinen P, Isolauri E.** 2001. Probiotics in primary prevention of atopic disease: a randomised placebo-controlled trial. *The Lancet* **357 (9262)**, 1076-1079.
- Kanazawa H, Nagino M, Kamiya S, Komatsu S, Mayumi T, Takagi K, Asahara T, Nomoto K, Tanaka R, Nimura Y.** 2005. Synbiotics reduce postoperative infectious complications: a randomized controlled trial in biliary cancer patients undergoing hepatectomy. *Langenbeck's Archives of Surgery* **390 (2)**, 104- 113.
- Karthikeyan N, Elango A, Kumaresan G, Gopalakrishnamurthy TR, Pandiyan C.** 2013. Augmentation of probiotic viability in ice cream using microencapsulation technique. *International Journal of Advanced Veterinary Science and Technology* **2(1)**, 76- 83.

- Karthikeyan N, Elango A, Kumaresan G, Gopalakrishnamurthy TR, Raghunath BV.** 2014. Enhancement of probiotic viability in ice cream by microencapsulation. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* **3(1)**, 339- 347.
- Kerry RG, Patra JK, Gouda S, Park Y, Shin HS, Das G.** 2018. Benefaction of probiotics for human health: A review. *Journal of Food and Drug Analysis* **26(3)**, 927- 939.
- Kia EM, Alizadeh M, Esmaili M.** 2018. Development and characterization of probiotic UF Feta cheese containing *Lactobacillus paracasei* microencapsulated by enzyme based gelation method. *Journal of Food Science and Technology* **55(9)**, 3657- 3664.
- Kolozyn-Krajewskaa D, Dolatowski ZJ.** 2012. Probiotic meat products and human nutrition. *Process Biochemistry* **47(12)**, 1761-1772.
- Korbekandi H, Mortazavian AM, Irvani S.** 2011. Technology and stability of probiotic in fermented milks. *Probiotic and Prebiotic Foods: Technology, Stability and Benefits to the Human Health* 131- 169.
- Krasaekoop W, Bhandari B, Deeth H.** 2003. Evaluation of encapsulation techniques of probiotics for yoghurt. *International Dairy Journal* **13 (1)**, 3-13.
- Krasaekoopt W, Bhandari B, Deeth H.** 2004. The influence of coating materials on some properties of alginate beads and survivability of microencapsulated probiotic bacteria. *International Dairy Journal* **14(8)**, 737- 743.
- Krishnan S, Kshirsagar AC, Singhal RS.** 2005. The use of gum arabic and modified starch in the microencapsulation of a food flavoring agent. *Carbohydrate Polymers* **62(4)**, 309- 315.
- Lin DC.** 2003. Probiotics as functional foods. *Nutrition in Clinical Practice* **18(6)**, 497- 506.
- Livney YD.** 2010. Milk proteins as vehicles for bio actives. *Current Opinion in Colloid and Interface Science* **15(1-2)**, 73- 83.
- Lopez-Rubio A, Gavara R, Lagaron JM.** 2006. Bioactive packaging: turning foods into healthier foods through biomaterials. *Trends in Food Science and Technology* **17(10)**, 567-575.
- Lourens-Hattingh A, Viljoen BC.** 2001. Yogurt as probiotic carrier food. *International Dairy Journal* **11(1)**, 1-17.
- Luckow T, Delahunty C.** 2004. Which juice is 'healthier'? A consumer study of probiotic non-dairy juice drinks. *Food Quality and Preference* **15(7)**, 751-759.
- Madene A, Jacquot M, Scher J, Desobry S.** 2006. Flavour encapsulation and controlled release—a review. *International Journal of Food Science and Technology* **41(1)**, 1- 21.
- Marco ML, De Vries MC, Wels M, Molenaar D, Mangell P, Ahrne S, De Vos WM, Vaughan EE, Kleerebezem M.** 2010. Convergence in probiotic *Lactobacillus* gut-adaptive responses in humans and mice. *The ISME Journal* **4(11)**, 1481-1484.
- Martín MJ, Lara-Villoslada F, Ruiz MA, Morales ME.** 2015. Microencapsulation of bacteria: A review of different technologies and their impact on the probiotic effects. *Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies* **27**, 15- 25.
- Mattila-Sandholm T, Myllarinen P, Crittenden R, Mogensen G, Fonden R, Saarela M.** 2002. Technological challenges for future probiotic foods. *International Dairy Journal* **12(2)**, 173-182.
- Messaoudi M, Lalonde R, Violle N, Javelot H, Desor D, Nejdj A, Bisson JF, Rougeot C, Pichelin M, Cazaubiel M, Cazaubiel JM.** 2011. Assessment of psychotropic-like properties of a probiotic formulation (*Lactobacillus helveticus* R0052 and *Bifidobacterium longum* R0175) in rats and human subjects. *British Journal of Nutrition* **105(5)**, 755-764.

- Mohammadi R, Mortazavian AM, Khosrokhavar R, da Cruz AG.** 2011. Probiotic ice cream: viability of probiotic bacteria and sensory properties. *Annals of Microbiology* **61(3)**, 411- 424.
- Mohammadi R, Mortazavian AM.** 2011. Technological aspects of prebiotics in probiotic fermented milks. *Food Reviews International* **27(2)**, 192- 212.
- Mokarram RR, Mortazavi SA, Najafi MBH, Shahidi F.** 2009. The influence of multistage alginate coating on survivability of potential probiotic bacteria in simulated gastric and intestinal juice. *Food Research International* **42(8)**, 1040- 1045.
- Mortazavian AM, Azizi A, Ehsani MR, Razavi SH, Mousavi SM, Sohrabvandi, Reinheimer JA.** 2008. Survival of encapsulated probiotic bacteria in Iranian yogurt drink (Doogh) after the product exposure to simulated gastrointestinal conditions. *Milk Science International* **63(4)**, 427- 429.
- Mortazavian AM, Ehsani MR, Azizi A, Razavi SH, Mousavi SM, Sohrabvandi S, Reinheimer JA.** 2008. Viability of calcium-alginate-microencapsulated probiotic bacteria in Iranian yogurt drink (Doogh) during refrigerated storage and under simulated gastrointestinal conditions. *Australian Journal of Dairy Technology* **63(1)**, 24-29.
- Nejati R, Gheisari HR, Hosseinzadeh S, Behbod M.** 2017. Viability of encapsulated *Lactobacillus acidophilus* (LA-5) in UF cheese and its survival under in vitro simulated gastrointestinal conditions. *International Journal of Dairy Technology* **70(1)**, 77- 83.
- Ningtyas DW, Bhandari B, Bansal N, Prakash S.** 2019. The viability of probiotic *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* (non-encapsulated and encapsulated) in functional reduced-fat cream cheese and its textural properties during storage. *Food Control* **100**, 8- 16.
- Nualkaekul S, Charalampopoulos D.** 2011. Survival of *Lactobacillus plantarum* in model solutions and fruit juices. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* **146(2)**, 111- 117.
- Oelschlaeger TA.** 2010. Mechanisms of probiotic actions—a review. *International Journal of Medical Microbiology* **300(1)**, 57- 62.
- Phillips M, Kailasapathy K, Tran L.** 2006. Viability of commercial probiotic cultures (*L. acidophilus*, *Bifidobacterium sp.*, *L. casei*, *L. paracasei* and *L. rhamnosus*) in cheddar cheese. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* **108(2)**, 276- 280.
- Picot A, Lacroix C.** 2004. Encapsulation of *Bifidobacteria* in whey protein-based microcapsules and survival in stimulated gastrointestinal conditions and in yoghurt. *International Dairy Journal* **14(6)**, 505-515.
- Pinto SS, Fritzen-Freire CB, Dias CO, Amboni RD.** 2019. A potential technological application of probiotic microcapsules in lactose-free Greek-style yoghurt. *International Dairy Journal* **97**, 131- 138.
- Poncelet D, Dreffier C.** 2007. Microencapsulation methods from A to Z (or almost). *Microencapsulation from Sciences to Technology* 23-33.
- Pradeep Prasanna PH, Charalampopoulos D.** 2019. Encapsulation in an alginate-goats' milk-inulin matrix improves survival of probiotic *Bifidobacterium* in simulated gastrointestinal conditions and goats' milk yoghurt. *International Journal of Dairy Technology* **72(1)**, 132-141.
- Prosapio V, Reverchon E, De Marco I.** 2016. Production of lysozyme microparticles to be used in functional foods, using an expanded liquid antisolvent process. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids* **107**, 106-113.
- Radulović Z, Miočinović J, Mirković N, Mirković M, Paunović D, Ivanović M, Seratlić S.** 2017. Survival of spray-dried and free-cells of potential probiotic *Lactobacillus plantarum* 564 in soft goat cheese. *Animal Science Journal* **88(11)**, 1849- 1854.
- Ranadheera CS, Evans CA, Adams MC, Baines SK.** 2012. In vitro analysis of gastrointestinal tolerance and intestinal cell adhesion of probiotics in goat's milk ice cream and yogurt. *Food Research International* **49(2)**, 619-625.

- Rasic JL.** 2003. Microflora of the intestine probiotics. In B.Caballero, L. Trugo, and P. Finglas (Eds.). Encyclopedia of Food Sciences and Nutrition. Oxford: Academic Press. 3911-3916
- Rayes N, Seehofer D, Theruvath T, Schiller RA, Langrehr JM, Jonas S, Bengmark S, Neuhaus P.** 2005 . Supply of pre-and probiotics reduces bacterial infection rates after liver transplantation—a randomized, double-blind trial. American Journal of Transplantation **5(1)**, 125-130.
- Reid G.** 2015. The growth potential for dairy probiotics. International Dairy Journal **49**, 16- 22.
- Reyes V, Chotiko A, Chouljenko A, Sathivel S.** 2018. Viability of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* NRRL B-4495 encapsulated with high maize starch, maltodextrin, and gum arabic. LWT **96**, 642- 647.
- Rivera-Espinoza Y, Gallardo-Navarro Y.** 2010. Non-dairy probiotic products. Food Microbiology **27(1)**, 1-11.
- Roberfroid MB.** 1999. What is beneficial for health? The concept of functional food. Food Chemistry and Toxicology **37**, 1039-1041.
- Rosenfeldt V, Benfeldt E, Valerius NH, Pærregaard A, Michaelsen KF.** 2004. Effect of probiotics on gastrointestinal symptoms and small intestinal permeability in children with atopic dermatitis. The Journal of Pediatrics **145(5)**, 612-616.
- Ross RP, Fitzgerald G, Collins K, Stanton C.** 2002. Cheese delivering biocultures: probiotic cheese. Australian Journal of Dairy Technology **57**, 71- 78.
- Sajilata MG, Singhal RS, Kulkarni PR.** 2006. Resistant starch—a review. Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety **5 (1)**, 1-17.
- Salem MM, Fathi FA, Awad RA.** 2005. Production of probiotic ice cream. Polish Journal of Food and Nutrition Sciences **14(3)**, 267.
- Santacruz S, Castro M.** 2018. Viability of free and encapsulated *Lactobacillus acidophilus* incorporated to cassava starch edible films and its application to Manaba fresh white cheese. LWT Food Science and Technology **93**, 570- 572.
- Semyonov D, Ramon O, Kaplun Z, Levin-Brener L, Gurevich N, Shimoni E.** 2010. Microencapsulation of *Lactobacillus paracasei* by spray freeze drying. Food Research International **43(1)**, 193-202.
- Sendra E, Fayos P, Lario Y, Fernández-López J, Sayas-Barberá E, Pérez-Alvarez JA.** 2008. Incorporation of citrus fibers in fermented milk containing probiotic bacteria. Food Microbiology **25(1)**, 13-21.
- Shah NP, Ravula R.** 2004. Selling the cells in desserts. Dairy Industries International **69(1)**, 31-32.
- Siro I, Kapolna E, Kapolna B, Lugasi A.** 2008. Functional food. Product development, marketing and consumer acceptance-A review. Appetite **51(3)**, 456-467.
- Sohail A, Turner MS, Coombes A, Bostrom T, Bhandari B.** 2011. Survivability of probiotics encapsulated in alginate gel microbeads using a novel impinging aerosols method. International Journal of Food Microbiology **145(1)**, 162- 168.
- Solanki HK, Pawar DD, Shah DA, Prajapati VD, Jani GK, Mulla AM, Thakar PM.** 2013. Development of microencapsulation delivery system for long-term preservation of probiotics as biotherapeutics agent. Biomedical Research International **2013**, 21.
- Song H, Yu W, Gao M, Liu X, Ma X.** 2013. Microencapsulated probiotics using emulsification technique coupled with internal or external gelation process. Carbohydrate polymers **96(1)**, 181- 189.
- Stanton C, Gardiner G, Meehan H, Collins K, Fitzgerald GF, Lynch PB, Ross RP.** 2001. Market potential for probiotics. The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition **73(2)**, 476- 483.

- Sultana K, Godward G, Reynolds N, Arumugaswamy R, Peiris P, Kailasapathy K.** 2000. Encapsulation of probiotic bacteria with alginate–starch and evaluation of survival in simulated gastrointestinal conditions and in yoghurt. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* **62 (1-2)**, 47- 55.
- Suvarna VC, Bobby VU.** 2005. Probiotics in human health: A current assessment. *Current Science* **88(11)**, 1744- 1748.
- Tripathi MK, Giri SK.** 2014. Probiotic functional foods: Survival of probiotics during processing and storage. *Journal of Functional Foods* **9**, 225- 241.
- Tsai YL, Lin TL, Chang CJ, Wu TR, Lai WF, Lu CC, Lai HC.** 2019. Probiotics, prebiotics and amelioration of diseases. *Journal of Biomedical Science* **26 (1)**, 1- 8.
- Tuomola EM, Ouwehand AC, Salminen SJ.** 2006. The effect of probiotic bacteria on the adhesion of pathogens to human intestinal mucus. *FEMS Immunology and Medical Microbiology* **26 (2)**, 137- 142.
- Ventura M, Perozzi G.** 2011. Probiotic bacteria and human gut microbiota. *Genes and Nutrition* **6(1)**, 203-204.
- Verbeke W.** 2005. Consumer acceptance of functional foods: socio-demographic, cognitive and attitudinal determinants. *Food Quality and Preference* **16 (1)**, 45- 57.
- Vinderola CG, Reinheimer JA.** 2003. Lactic acid bacteria: A comparative “*in vitro*” study of probiotic characteristics and biological barrier resistance. *Food Research International* **36 (9-10)**, 895- 904.
- Wattananapakasem I, van Valenberg HJ, Fogliano V, Costabile A, Suwannaporn P.** 2018. Synbiotic microencapsulation from slow digestible colored rice and its effect on yoghurt quality. *Food and Bioprocess Technology* **11(6)**, 1111-1124.
- Yoon WB, Mccarthy KL.** 2002. Rheology of yogurt during pipe flow as characterized by magnetic resonance imaging. *Journal of Texture Studies* **33(5)**, 431- 444.
- Zanjani MAK, Ehsani MR, Ghiassi Tarzi B, Sharifan A.** 2018. Promoting *Lactobacillus casei* and *Bifidobacterium adolescentis* survival by microencapsulation with different starches and chitosan and poly L-lysine coatings in ice cream. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation* **42(1)**, 13318.
- Zinedine A, Faid M.** 2007. Isolation and characterization of strains of *Bifidobacteriawith* probiotic proprieties in vitro. *World Journal of Dairy and Food Science* **2(1)**, 28-34.
- Zuidam NJ, Shimoni E.** 2009. Overview of microencapsulates for use in food products or processes and methods to take them. *Encapsulation Technologies for Active Food Ingredients and Food Processing* 3-29.